

A Critical Literature Review of County
Lines Gang Activity, the Harms of Child
Criminal Exploitation and the Adequacy of
Government Responses.

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Abstract

This dissertation aims to explore the harms caused to young people by Child Criminal Exploitation from within County Lines drug gangs. It aims to review academic literature such as journal articles and books to gain an understanding of the severe implications that this type of exploitation can have. This project uses government reports and evaluations to develop knowledge around the effectiveness of responses implemented by the government to reduce this threat. This is because county lines gangs target vulnerable young people and children and proceed to coerce and manipulate them into criminal activities. They then use extreme violence and intimidation to ensure the young people are unable to leave and reach support. It was found that young people are manipulated through grooming tactics that are based on their perceived vulnerability such as a lack of parental supervision. Also, there is a significant impact on the role that the social environment and community has on how young people end up trapped within county lines gangs. Moreover, another main finding was the damaging physical and psychological harm that is inflicted on young people throughout their engagement with gang members. Also, within chapter 2, it was found that there have been improvements in supporting young people after they have been exploited, but an overall lack of provisions for preventing child criminal exploitation in the first place which identifies where progress needs to be made within tackling county lines gangs. Therefore, further research should prioritize investigation into how social inequalities leads young people to engage in county lines gangs and criminal activities.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This dissertation aims to explore County Lines drug gangs and the Child Criminal Exploitation (CCE) that takes place within them because they pose a significant threat to vulnerable adults and children. Demonstrated in this research project is a concerning high level of risk to young people that needs to be investigated before it causes significant long-lasting damage to children's lives. This is due to the extensive amount of harm young people experience at the hands of county lines gang members. Therefore, this research is justified because young people have the right to safety and protection, and to not be at risk of exploitation which is not possible with these gangs targeting them and placing them in difficult situations that they struggle to escape from. In addition, County Lines are fairly new within society which identifies why government responses need evaluating to discuss where improvements can be made, in order to limit the exposure of unnecessary harm to young people. However, there is not a vast amount of academic literature on this topic which shows the importance of this research because it is vital to further the understanding on the effectiveness of strategies in not only reducing county lines gangs but also in preventing CCE and offering support to victims.

1.2 Research Question, Aims & Objectives

What are the harmful effects of Child Criminal Exploitation on the young people involved in 'County Lines' drug gangs, and are government responses effective in reducing this threat?

1.2.1 Research Aims:

- Highlight the reasons as to why and how children and young people are targeted for exploitation within County Lines operations.
- Examine the harm and negative implications being involved in 'County Lines' Child Criminal Exploitation (CCE) has on victims.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of government responses in dealing with child criminal exploitation within county Lines gangs.

1.2.2 Research Objectives:

- Investigating journal articles and research papers through the university library website 'Discover', Google Scholar, PsycINFO, Sage Journals Online, Taylor and Francis Online, Scopus, Research in Practice, and Academic Search Complete to collate information regarding county lines gangs and Child Criminal Exploitation.

- To search the literature to identify the significant harms associated with County Lines gangs and young people.
- Analysing government reports and academic resources to demonstrate different Home Office responses and evaluating their role in tackling CCE within County Lines.
- To synthesize the information gathered to develop an in-depth understanding of Child Criminal Exploitation in county Lines drug gangs and the responses that are provided by the government.

1.3 Methodology & Ethical Considerations

To achieve the aims and objectives of this project, the most appropriate choice of methodology was to conduct a literature-based dissertation. According to Young (2022) this type of dissertation involves gathering and critically analysing previous academic research and implementing theoretical concepts to gain further knowledge around a chosen topic. Additionally, this method allows for the development of arguments that bring together information that has not been previously linked together. Furthermore, the use of a narrative literature review summarises relevant research because it helps to identify gaps in knowledge and develop the justification for this research project (Clark et al, 2021). It also benefits social research by suiting a wide range of criminological fields that can be studied in detail, however, some limitations include not being able to provide a clear methodology section and it may not result in any significant practical applications for future advancements as there could be a lack of high-quality research available (Davies and Francis, 2018). Also, relying on other people's research creates the risk of having potentially unreliable sources that could significantly impact the findings.

Furthermore, in this dissertation a variety of databases is used to identify specific books, academic journal articles and research papers that are relevant to my research question; these include the Leeds Beckett University library website 'Discover', Google Scholar, PsycINFO, Sage Journals Online, Scopus, and Academic Search Complete. Furthermore, the search terms used to narrow down the amount of information available included County Lines gangs, Child Criminal Exploitation, vulnerable young people and children, experiences of harm, government responses and strategies, effectiveness, prevention, and support for victims. The criteria set did not include resources from before 2015 and involved research based in England and Wales to ensure that it is relevant to this project and is the most recent data available.

In social research, ethical guidelines must be followed to ensure good practice takes place and that participants are protected (British Society of Criminology, 2015). There are several principles which include gaining informed consent, preventing an invasion of privacy, maintaining participants

confidentiality, and to do no harm (Greetham, 2019). Therefore, a strength of choosing a literature-based dissertation is that it limits the number of ethical issues that could develop (Young, 2022). This project contains research on the exploitation of vulnerable young people and would not be appropriate to conduct primary research due to the risk of causing additional harm which can range from physical, psychological, stress, or low self-esteem (Clark et al, 2021). Also, gaining informed consent could have raised issues during the research process because of the age of possible participants and because they may not have a full understanding of the purpose of this project it could impact the results, as well as brake ethical principles. These concerns justified the decision to complete a literature-based dissertation to prioritise the wellbeing of participants. Ethical approval was granted for this dissertation from the Research Ethics Policy and Procedures of Leeds Beckett University.

1.4 Outline of Dissertation

This dissertation includes a literature review, and two chapters that are based on themes collated from the research found. The purpose of the literature review is to gain an understanding of past research on county lines and to outline the different components within these gangs such as the hierarchy, the impact of 'Cuckooing', and the role that vulnerable young people take when engaging in these types of gangs. It will also examine the extent to which exploitation of vulnerable adults and children is a concerning issue that needs more academic research. Further, it will introduce the theory involved throughout this dissertation to explore the reasons behind CCE within County Lines gangs. Next, chapter one examines the underlying reasons behind why and how young people are targeted by county lines; for example, coercion and grooming is a large factor. It will then detail the significant extent of the physical and psychological harms that young people are subjected to because of the gangs' violent behaviour which demonstrates the urgent need for further research. Finally, the second chapter analyses and evaluates three different Government responses to tackling CCE within county lines gangs; this is an important aspect because reducing the risk of harm to young people is vital and strategies need to be working effectively for this to happen.

Chapter 2: Background, Key Concepts & Theory

This literature review will examine the existing research surrounding the topic of County Lines Criminal Gangs and the specific forms of exploitation that takes place within them. To begin, it will explain what county lines consists of using a variety of Government and academic definitions. After, the theory that will be used throughout this dissertation is introduced; it will examine adverse childhood experiences and build on Matza's (1964) theory of delinquency and drift to further understand the reasons why young people are exploited within County Lines gangs. Next, it will explore the hierarchy within these gangs and how vulnerable young people are used as drug runners (Coomber and Moyle, 2018); this is important to consider because it begins to show the extent of the harm they experience. Then, it will explain how the exploitation of adults and children is involved in County Lines through coercion and manipulation (Robinson et al, 2019). The next section will introduce Child Criminal Exploitation, including who and why certain young individuals are targeted; this will start to provide significant detail on why understanding Child Criminal Exploitation is necessary when examining government responses.

The Home Office (2023a) defines 'County Lines' as a form of organised crime that involves the movement of illegal drugs from one place within the UK to another through the exploitation of vulnerable people. According to Spicer (2018), London is where these drug gangs originated, and they have expanded from there. It has been identified that 69% of the drugs distributed through county lines is crack and heroin (National Crime Agency, 2018), although evidence has suggested that other types of drugs such as cannabis are also dealt on the side to increase profits (National Crime Agency, 2018). Furthermore, according to the County Line Programme data collected by the Home Office (2024) there has been a total of 5,627 county lines closed by agencies such as the Police; as well as 16,536 arrests made so far. This evidence suggests a concerning level of threat and large scale of county lines criminal gangs within the UK.

Moreover, Coomber and Moyle (2018) state that the exportation of these drugs is focused on moving away from the gangs' urban base to rural towns that are a significant distance away; this is done to avoid competition from other dealers as well as to lower the risk of being noticed by the police. Coomber and Pyle (2015) cited in Spicer et al (2019) identified heroin to have been exported from Liverpool all the way to Torbay; this is over 250 miles and shows how far the dealers are willing to go. Additionally, the drug dealers will use "dedicated mobile phone lines" (Home Office, 2018, p.48) to

facilitate the importing of their product to specific areas. This is to allow purchases to be made and then orders to be delivered by the drug 'runners' which is overseen by leaders in the city (Spicer, 2018). It is done this way to limit detection by police forces, making it harder for agencies to identify where the county line is running from allowing for the base to be established quickly (O'Hagan and Long, 2019).

Moving forward, the following section of this literature review will introduce the theory that will be prevalent throughout this project and will begin to explain why young people are targeted and exploited by county lines criminal gangs. This dissertation will examine and link together adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) and David Matza's theory of Delinquency and Drift, developed in 1964. Firstly, a definition of adverse childhood experiences is provided by Windle et al (2020) which suggests that certain negative events such as abuse (including verbal, physical, sexual and emotional); as well as traumatic experiences ranging from parents suffering from mental illness, substance misuse, domestic violence or family deaths can all increase the likelihood that young people may be exploited into criminal gangs due to their vulnerability. Maxwell (2024) suggests that in cases where children have unmet needs through experiencing any of these adverse childhood experiences, are at risk of drifting into exploitative situations. However, this original framework of adverse childhood experiences has been found to be too simplistic. McEwen and Gregerson (2019) argue that it does not consider wider social factors such as poverty and social inequality; or harms within the community including racism or witnessing violence that also have an impact on childhood.

To address this issue, a tool created by Ellis and Dietz which is mentioned in Windle et al (2020) known as The Pair of ACEs Tree demonstrates the wide variety of experiences in childhood and the wider community that cause long-lasting physical and mental illnesses, as well as the inability to cope in certain situations. Furthermore, the tree considers underlying issues such as limited opportunities, discrimination, and poverty; these social problems are visualised as the soil that tree roots are encompassed in because it highlights inequalities that restrict the steady growth and development of young people (Windle et al, 2020). This indicates that young people who have experienced not only childhood adversities but also community deprivations may be at a higher risk of exploitation by county lines gangs due to their increased vulnerability. Therefore, this knowledge is vital and should be used to guide future government policies and prevention strategies to help reduce the exploitation of children. However, it is important to state that this Pair of ACEs Tree by Ellis and Dietz found in Windle et al (2020) was sourced from a news website which raises concern as to the reliability of the information when used in an academic journal article and should be used with caution.

Further, David Matza produced the theory of delinquency and drift. According to Lilly et al (2018) Matza argued that for a young person to drift into criminality they go through several processes. The first is preparation which involves an individual learning that they can engage in these acts, as well as them learning that being caught by authorities can to some extent be avoided. Secondly, Lilly et al (2018) states that desperation plays an important role, this is because if an individual feels overwhelmed or is struggling at home, crime becomes a way of showing their individuality and reasserting a level of control within their life. Furthermore, adverse childhood experiences builds on Matza's theory because if a child has experienced significant trauma or has an unstable home life then they may attempt to find security in solutions the gang members are offering (Maxwell, 2024). Likewise, Blomberg et al (2017) outlines Matza's argument regarding young people's inability to rationally choose to engage in crime because they are malleable and dependent on adults for guidance which can be exploited. This indicates that factors such as social inequalities and inadequate parental and educational engagement in children's lives can lead to criminal exploitation within county lines drug gangs.

Turning now, to explore the hierarchy within County Lines that demonstrate the roles that specific individuals have. The out-of-town dealers are at the top where they stay away from engagement with the drug users in their rural locations and only involving themselves in organising and exploiting other people to avoid being detected by law enforcement (Windle et al, 2020). Further down in the structure, are members known as 'sitters' who are responsible for supervising the supply at the rural base; and according to Coomber and Moyle (2018, p.1335) they act as protective "drug custodians." At the bottom of the hierarchy are the 'runners' who are often young people and children that have been exploited and are coerced into distributing and making sales to users out on the streets (Coomber and Moyle, 2018). This puts the vulnerable young people into precarious and unsafe situations when being tasked with transporting drugs, money, and in some cases dangerous weapons to and from the urban and rural bases (McClean et al, 2020). These are examples of the negative impacts that county lines can have on young people due to the risk of harm and the likelihood they might be apprehended by the police. Furthermore, in these situations the young people are viewed as easily dispensable which is evidenced by the risky environments they are placed in; this links in with the pair of ACEs tree theory because clearly more support is needed to prevent exploitation within local communities. These implications suggest that it is necessary to explore further into the harms caused by County Lines drug gangs.

Moreover, the following section introduces exploitation as a key aspect of the county lines drug supply model in which vulnerable adults and children are used to transport and deal drugs. Robinson et al

(2019) shows how vulnerable adults are exploited for various reasons such as their drug use, for 'cuckooing', or through manipulation which can involve sexual violence, coercion and intimidation tactics. The dealers usually target drug users because they are easily coerced through wanting access to drugs, they are then put into drug debts and forced to work it off through selling drugs. Harding (2020) also suggests that to maximise profits the strategy of 'cuckooing' is used, this includes taking over a vulnerable person's home and using it as a base to store and sell drugs. There are a variety of different people that can be victims of cuckooing, these include the elderly, people with mental health issues or disabilities, drug users, and sex workers (Spicer et al, 2019). In some cases, the cuckooed homes have children and young people living within them; they too are then subjected to significant exploitation and are forced to undertake criminal activities and live in unsuitable environments (Stone, 2018). This dissertation will focus on examining the negative impacts this has on the young people rather than the adults who also experience exploitation.

Additionally, Mclean et al (2020) identified that until recently there has been a gap in the academic literature on county lines and the significant impact that Child Criminal Exploitation (CCE) has on the young people involved. The Government defines CCE as an abuse of power from other people towards someone under the age of 18 for criminal gain; this can be done online or in person through coercion and manipulation (Home Office, 2018). However, Pearson and Cavener (2024) state that a definition involving CCE and County Lines combined has not been provided which makes it difficult for professionals to identify risk factors and give support needed to young people. Moreover, according to Windle et al (2020), the dealers usually target young boys aged between 14-17 years old, although they have been known to target children as young as age 7 (Neaverson and Lake, 2023); this is because they can be easily manipulated through cheap ways and then disposed of quickly if needed. However, it has been found that young girls and women are becoming increasingly involved in County Lines through coercion and often sexual violence from gang members (Harding, 2020). Evidence shown by Havard et al (2023) suggests that young girls are usually exploited into these gangs through the belief of a relationship with a male member or other emotional or physically abusive behaviour. Moreover, O'Hagan and Edmundson (2021), indicates that the young people are criminally exploited and used to move drugs between different locations, as well as distribute and sell it to users at the rural hub which puts them in risky and harmful situations. This is achieved by providing the young people with tangible rewards such as money, the prospect of a career, or the chance of a family structure, which after exploitation turns into threats of violence (Robinson et al, 2019). These methods of exploitation support the theory of young people being pushed towards criminal activity because a lack of opportunities for income or basic necessities leads them to engage in drug dealing for survival (Maxwell, 2024).

In addition, due to young people being forced into criminal tasks there is some controversy about whether these vulnerable individuals are to be classed as victims or offenders (Moyle, 2019); some researchers believe that although their actions may appear consensual, this does not mean the child or young person has not been exploited. Additionally, Harvard et al (2023) found that in some cases of abuse within these gangs, questions have been raised as to the young women's victim or offender status because of stereotypes around gender roles within gangs which leads to female victims not receiving vital support. This evidence suggests that further exploration is needed to develop a stronger understanding of Child Criminal Exploitation within County Lines criminal gangs.

In conclusion, this literature review has examined research on County Lines Criminal gangs. This research set out to explore what this drug distribution system consisted of and found that it is a significant national threat because of the severity of harm caused by these gangs (Home Office, 2024). Furthermore, key theories were introduced which will be relevant throughout this dissertation because they help to gain a better understanding as to why children and young people are targeted by county lines. Additionally, research shows that the concept of exploitation is extremely prevalent within county lines gangs, with vulnerable adults and children being at high risk. However, one important finding was the lack of research into the harms caused by Child Criminal Exploitation within county lines until recently (McClean et al, 2020) and is therefore one of the main focuses in this project. This is because it is crucial to understand what causes young people to be targeted, and what harms and future implications it leads to; this will be examined in the next chapter.

Chapter 3: Why and How Young People Are Targeted by County Lines Gangs, and the Harms Associated with This Involvement.

As discussed in the previous chapter, Child Criminal Exploitation is a large component of county lines gangs. According to the Home Office (2024), data collected from the County Lines Programme in the year 2022/23 there was estimated to be “14,000 children at risk or involved in child criminal exploitation”; although they state that it is likely to be on a much larger scale. This shows how vital it is that researchers understand the specific techniques used to target vulnerable young people to help reduce the risk. Therefore, this chapter will begin by examining what makes young people more susceptible to exploitation, and why gangs choose to do this. Next, this chapter will move on to discuss how county lines gang members groom and coerce young people into believing that engaging with the gang will benefit them. Unfortunately, this is not the case and the repercussions of involvement with county lines are destructive to young people and their families; this leads into the last section of this chapter which will highlight personal accounts and reports of the physical and psychological harms caused by county lines gangs to bring attention to the serious risk that young people face.

The first section of this chapter will focus on exploring why county lines gangs target children and young people. To begin, Andell and Pitts (2018) note that these gangs are more likely to target young people who are involved with Youth Offending Teams, as well as Children’s Services because their vulnerability makes them susceptible to exploitation. It is also common for gang members to target their own family members (Maxwell, 2023). This is because young people are viewed as cheap labour and can be disposed of quickly by gang members which makes them ideal for the dangerous activities within the drug distribution process including selling drugs on the street (Coomber and Moyle, 2018). There is also evidence of county lines gangs targeting children who are experiencing homelessness or poverty because it provides them with opportunities to manipulate the young person into believing that they can have a better life or future career prospects (Stone, 2018). Additionally, Stone (2018) identified that drug dealers will target young people due to their lack of criminal convictions as it lowers the risk of them getting caught and attracting the attention of the police. These factors increase the likelihood of CCE by county lines gangs and are seen in the Pair of ACEs Tree (Windle et al, 2020) which indicates that researchers should be exploring the role that the wider community and society plays in young

people ending up trapped within county lines and not placing sole responsibility on the child themselves or their parents.

Moving forward, the next section will examine the specific manipulation tactics that county lines gang members have been known to use in order to exploit children and young people into engaging in criminal activities. According to O'Hagan and Long (2019) these are known as pull factors because young people feel it is an easy solution to change their current circumstances. Firstly, it has been identified that coercion and grooming are extreme techniques used which includes gang members buying young people gifts, stolen products, or money to lure them in (Mclean et al, 2020). According to Atkinson-Sheppard et al (2023) this type of coercion occurs first because it is effective in creating the illusion of a safe and inviting environment that attracts young people. However, after the young person has been groomed into believing they have a friendship with gang members the exploitation intensifies, and they are put into increasingly risky situations. For example, Atkinson-Sheppard et al (2023) shows that interpersonal coercion is a significant aspect during the exploitation process where physical violence, threatening behaviour and debt bondage are frequently used to trap young people into county lines gangs. Furthermore, it is suggested that social factors such as poverty which is also known as impersonal coercion leads to involvement in county lines because of desperate situations. However, it is important to note that Atkinson-Sheppard et al (2023) found that for some young people this is not always the case because even those who were surrounded by stable environments and had access to a good level of education were exploited by county lines. This suggests that the consistency and persuasiveness of the coercive techniques used has more of an impact rather than the specific child they target.

Additionally, these next sections will discuss how drug dealers manipulate young people into engaging with county lines. A study conducted by Maxwell (2024) involved interviewing young people who had been exploited by county lines and found that money played a significant part in this process. According to Maxwell (2024) several young individuals were targeted because they needed money for necessities such as food and clothes which infers a level of deprivation and vulnerability that is used to coerce and groom young people into county lines. However, it is necessary to state that these experiences are not fully representative of all young people who have been exploited because the participants were all male which does not account for the many females that are exploited (Maxwell, 2024). Nevertheless, this evidence links in with Matza's (1964) theory because issues such as starvation and other unmet needs can cause individuals to drift into criminal activity out of desperation (Lilly et al, 2018). On the other hand, research shows that young people felt that what the drug dealers were offering was an

opportunity to become rich and successful; this is further supported by Robinson et al (2019) who found that some victims of CCE did not appreciate being labelled a victim because it was an easy way to make money, and they felt they had no other option due to their age and lack of education. This suggests that a lack of employment opportunities for young people or the assumption that they do not have any appropriate qualifications creates the belief that gang membership and criminal activities are a suitable alternative.

Also, it has been found that gang membership provides vulnerable young people with the concept of a family structure that they may be lacking elsewhere (Robinson et al, 2019). A case study evidenced in Andell and Pitts (2023) further supports this as it was found that county lines gangs provide young people with a sense of belonging even when faced with dangerous situations. However, Maxwell (2023) found that gang members have been known to manipulate young people into believing that their families don't want them and that they would be better off in county lines as a way of getting them to engage. Furthermore, according to Moyle (2019) the gang provides them with feelings of significance and status, however this is often short-lived as the exploitation process becomes increasingly demanding and violent. This evidence shows that adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) is relevant here because it is possible that inadequate parental supervision and support can cause young people to search for it through other means, such as seeking the validation of being a part of county lines gangs (Windle et al, 2020).

Moreover, the following section of this chapter will explore the role of debt bondage within CCE and how out-of-town dealers use it to trap young people. According to Harding (2020), there are several reasons as to why drug dealers place young people in debt bondage; this includes taking or losing either money or drugs from elder gang members, not paying back loans, and issues when dealing the drugs to users. This evidence suggests that drug debt is a way of maintaining order within county lines and is used to outline the hierarchy, especially to show the young people that they are at the bottom. Furthermore, Robinson et al (2019) found that in Merseyside, young people used cannabis regularly which gang members used to lure them in with the promise of access to drugs. However, after the young people used what was provided it was made clear that the drugs were not free, and they would be put into drug debts which required them to take part in dealing to pay it off. Additionally, a technique that has been frequently used is known as fake robbery which Harding (2020) identifies as a strategy created to control individuals within the gang. In an interview conducted with a young person who had been exploited by county lines, Atkinson-Sheppard (2024) found that it was common for gang members to conduct fake robberies on their own drug runners which included taking drugs and cash from them;

this was done to manipulate them into debt for a long period of time. Overall, debt bondage is a way of gang members exerting power and control over young people, Andell and Pitts (2023) suggests that this deception leads young people to believe that their only option is to carry on dealing drugs, therefore creating a vicious cycle that they struggle to escape from.

Likewise, another technique that is constantly adapting to a changing society is the use of social media to exploit young people into county lines gangs. Storrod and Densley (2017) found that social media makes it easier to offer a lavish lifestyle to young people. Social media glamorises gang involvement and reinforces the notion that gang life is desirable through large amounts of cash and expensive jewellery or clothing (Neaverson and Lake, 2023). Research conducted by Irwin-Rogers (2019) found that on social media platforms such as Instagram and YouTube there is evidence of young people wanting to move away from poverty and desperate living situations. These posts show how inequality, discrimination, and a lack of opportunities push young people into county lines gangs to fulfil basic needs. These ACEs coupled with images and videos portrayed on social media of what drug dealing could provide them with, leads to the exploitation of vulnerable young people. Moreover, Storrod and Densley (2017) state that after the initial grooming and contact is made, social media is used as a way of tracking a young person's location in order for gang members to assert control over them. The young people in this study stated that if they did not comply with tasks given to them by gang members there would consequences that consisted of physical or sexual violence (Storrod and Densley, 2017); therefore, the harms of these young people will be examined in the next section of this chapter because it is important to understand the extent to which county lines gangs are a severe threat to the safety and wellbeing of children and young people.

So far, this chapter has demonstrated why and how young people are exploited by county lines criminal gangs; this provides an understanding of the risk posed by these groups as evidence shows they will go to extreme lengths to coerce vulnerable individuals. Consequently, the CCE witnessed here leads to significant harm which is the focus of the next sections. To begin, Andell and Pitts (2023) show that once a young person has been criminally exploited and is coerced into selling drugs they are put into unsafe environments and the situation can become very hostile. It has been suggested by Moyle (2019, p.751) that within county lines gangs there is a "spectrum of harm" which infers a wide variety including physical, psychological, and sexual harm.

The first part of this section will explore accounts of young people and their families' experiences of physical violence during their exploitation within county lines gangs. Atkinson-Sheppard et al (2023) found evidence of physical violence as a way of coercing young people into engaging in criminal

activities for the gang; in this study a mother explained how her son was exploited by county lines and would consistently have injuries ranging from cuts, bruises, broken bones, and an incident of being stabbed. This is further supported by Robinson et al (2019, p.702) who interviewed young people that had been criminally exploited, they found that the concept of drug debt often led to experiences of “kidnapping, sexual violence, and torture.” These accounts show the extreme extent to which gang members will use violence to achieve control and maintain profit when dealing drugs. It is clear that abuse is used to create fear and ensure that victims are reluctant to report harmful incidents and avoid seeking help.

Furthermore, Harding (2020) describes a method known as ‘plugging’ that involves young people being instructed to insert condoms filled with drugs into their vagina or rectum as a way of concealing and transporting the drugs. It is also indicated that drugs are hidden in their cheeks because they can be swallowed by the young person if stopped by the police (O’Hagan and Edmundson, 2021). Additionally, there are reports of elder gang members using a strategy called ‘dinking’ on young people; this involves stabbing or inserting a knife into the anus to cut the rectum which causes significant harm and scarring (Harding, 2020). This is used as a punishment and makes sure that the young person will not be able to insert and carry drugs in the future. These incidents are extremely dangerous and Atkinson-Sheppard et al (2023) found it to have detrimental effects that are long-term both physically and psychologically due to the trauma caused by the injury.

Moreover, County lines gangs often take over a vulnerable person’s home which is known as ‘cuckooing’ and use it as a base to sell drugs, the young people who have been exploited are sent there to complete tasks such as transporting drugs, weapons, and money (McLean et al, 2020). According to Windle and Briggs (2015) they are forced to live in unhygienic conditions, surrounded by individuals who are using heroin and crack cocaine regularly which makes for an unsafe and violent environment. Furthermore, from their research Ashton and Bussu (2020) found that young people had issues with sleeping and often used cannabis to self-medicate when at a base which is usually in an area unknown to them. This is also supported by Dando et al (2023, p.350) who stated in an interview with parents of children who had been exploited that they were “filthy, thin and tired”. This indicates a lack of food and cleanliness, and an overall highly stressful environment that is not appropriate for children and young people to live in. It also provides evidence of Matza’s theory because if a child has unmet needs which is clear that the gangs do not provide them, then they are more likely to drift towards other methods such as crime for survival, for example a young person may turn to theft if they do not have access to food.

Additionally, this section will explore the risky and dangerous behaviours that young people engage in when being involved in county lines gangs and the impact it has on them. Research from Dando et al (2023) gathered through interviewing parents about their experiences of CCE found a common theme of sudden behavioural changes in their children which included carrying offensive weapons; for example, one parent stated, “he swore at a teacher, and a couple of his friendship group were caught selling drugs at school, then he had a knife” (Dando et al, 2023, p.349). These findings are very concerning because it puts the safety of the children themselves and other people at risk of significant harm, especially when young people may not fully comprehend how much damage they can cause by carrying weapons. Furthermore, according to the Ministry of Justice (2024) in 2023/24 “3,206 10 to 17-year-olds” were sentenced for knife and offensive weapon offences. It has been suggested that due to the violent nature of county lines and the consistent use of physical harm, young people are adapting their survival techniques which evidenced by the Ministry of Justice is using weapons to protect themselves (O’Hagan and Long, 2019). This shows that young people are at serious risk of harm from knife-related crimes and county lines gangs are part of a wider problem that needs addressing.

Turning now, to demonstrate how young girls are victims of significant harm when exploited within county lines gangs. Young girls are increasingly being used as ‘drug runners’ and have been found to be sexually assaulted and raped by older gang members (O’Hagan and Long, 2019). This is further supported by Andell and Pitts (2023) who found that young girls are often expected to submit to sexual acts, regardless of if they give consent because it is used as a form of coercive control. In addition, girls who are used as runners are instructed to hide drugs in their vaginal cavity which often leads to gang members sexually assaulting them to locate the drugs (Harding, 2020). Furthermore, evidence gathered from interviews with practitioners found that the fear created from threats of violence and sexual abuse was significant and leads to young girls being unable to contact the authorities which limits their access to support (Havard et al, 2023). However, it is important to mention that these crimes fall under and are better understood through Child Sexual Exploitation rather than Child Criminal Exploitation which is the primary focus of this project; although this does not mean to diminish the serious harm caused to young girls who are forced to experience these crimes.

Moving forward, this section will explore the psychological harms that happen during and after child criminal exploitation within county lines gangs. At the beginning of the exploitative process, Maxwell (2023) provides evidence from semi-structured interviews with the parents of criminally exploited young people that shows a common theme of children not engaging with school and spending more time with peer groups; as well as their demeanour and behaviour changing significantly. In addition,

Dando et al (2023) found that when young people had been exploited their mood changed drastically, this was from the viewpoint of their mothers and they stated that aggression, swearing, and being closed off from others were key developments that caused concern. However, it is important to note that many parents in these studies attributed this change to normal adolescent behaviour because developmentally they were around the age where they would have been experiencing puberty and therefore, this was often missed as a sign of exploitation (Maxwell, 2023).

Furthermore, the experiences that young people witness such as drug use and extreme violence have significant impacts on their mental health and wellbeing. This is demonstrated by Atkinson-Sheppard et al (2023) who states that young people were threatened with harm towards family members, in one case threats had been made to petrol bomb their homes and in another case a family member was severely harmed. The gang members are causing emotional distress as it will make sure to keep the young people involved out of fear for their families lives. Furthermore, Dando et al (2023) stated that one mother described living in fear and being scared for her son, this is because he had already been a victim of two shootings. This is not only physical harm inflicted by county lines gang members, but also immense psychological distress caused to the young person and his family.

Additionally, Whittaker et al (2018) highlights a report from Public Health England in 2015 on the mental health needs of gang affiliated young people; this report details how being involved with gangs can have a negative impact on their mental health and how consistent exposure to violence is associated with depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, and anxiety. Furthermore, evidence from Atkinson-Sheppard (2024) states that young people reported heightened anxiety and paranoia which led them to consistently watch their backs out of fear of being harmed, and in some cases choosing to carry weapons to protect themselves. The psychological harm to young people is significant and has long-lasting effects on their mental health. This is supported by Wood and Dennard (2017) who found that street gang prisoners gathered from a Youth Offenders Institute had witnessed more violence, had higher levels of post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, and paranoia compared to non-gang prisoners. This suggests that the large amount of violence experienced in county lines gangs has detrimental effects on young people and needs addressing. However, Wood and Dennard (2017) highlight that further research should be completed to gain a stronger understanding of gang membership in young males and females and subsequent mental health issues as their research is limited in the variety of participants.

In conclusion, this chapter set out to understand the serious risk that county lines gangs pose to young people. Research showed how and why young people are targeted with reasons ranging from them

being easily manipulated and disposable (Coomber and Moyle, 2018), as well as their vulnerability which makes grooming easier through offering access to money, drugs, and the prospect of a family structure (McLean et al, 2020). The coercion techniques used such as debt bondage and access to social media means young people struggle to escape from these gangs and is difficult for them to reach support. Often during their time involved in county lines the young people are subjected to and witness extreme physical and psychological harm, including knife-related injuries, shootings, assault, kidnap, torture, and sexual violence (Dando et al, 2023). There are also several reports about the severe psychological damage which involves post-traumatic stress disorder, high anxiety levels, issues with sleep, and paranoia (Atkinson-Sheppard, 2024). Overall, this chapter highlights the significant impact that county lines criminal gangs have on the young people they exploit. The evidence found is very concerning and raises questions regarding what is being done to tackle child criminal exploitation from happening to others. Therefore, the next chapter of this dissertation will investigate the effectiveness of Government responses to CCE within county lines gangs.

Chapter 4: Critically Discussing The Effectiveness of Government Responses

With this growing threat of county lines gangs and the exploitation of children and young people within them, it is crucial to explore the effectiveness of government responses in tackling CCE. As a result of the evidence found in chapter one, it is clearly an issue that urgently needs to be addressed because of the risk posed to young people. Therefore, this chapter will begin by understanding whether criminally exploited young people are considered to be victims or offenders in these situations due to the impact it could have on the support provided. After, three different responses will be discussed including the Serious Violence Strategy which involves the 'hospital-navigator' programme, the County Lines Programme and the British Transport Police, and finally, the use of Trusted Adult Workers. Within these sections, the aims and roles of these responses are outlined which helps provide a further understanding of whether they are efficient in dealing with CCE. Additionally, by using government reports and academic research articles the effectiveness of these responses is evaluated because it is important to demonstrate whether there are sufficient resources available to vulnerable young people and whether they are being supported and offered opportunities for a better future.

Firstly, before this chapter investigates the effectiveness of government responses in dealing with child criminal exploitation within county lines gangs it is important to gain an understanding of the victim or offender status. Marshall (2024) conducted interviews with several youth justice practitioners and found that young people were more likely to be viewed as victims of CCE if they disclosed to practitioners that they were being exploited. This is because it is not often that young people are open about details regarding what they were experiencing and therefore would be seen as genuine fear. On the other hand, young people who did not provide information to the police about the gang or drug dealing due to fear of negative consequences, led to it being assumed that they had something to hide, making it likely that they would be treated as a suspect (Marshall, 2024). Furthermore, Thompson (2019) identified that young people were often unaware that they were becoming engaged in activities that would mean being a part of county lines gangs. This is because they are groomed and coerced by someone they trust; this raises questions around young people's involvement and whether it is appropriate to treat them as offenders if they did not know what was happening or how to disengage from these activities (Thompson, 2019). Additionally, Oswald et al (2024) found that gender and

ethnicity had an impact on victim or offender status; if the young person was a young male from black and/or ethnic minority backgrounds then they were less likely to be considered a victim of CCE due to discriminatory prejudice within society. Consequently, these implications will have a significant impact on the support provided and is important to understand when examining the effectiveness of government responses.

To begin, the Home Office (2018) introduced the Serious Violence Strategy, included in this was a plan to tackle County Lines drug gangs because of the significant harm caused by its exploitative processes and drug distribution. It involves several government agencies ranging from the Department of Education to the National Police Chief's Council (NPCC) working together to reduce this threat. According to the Home Office (2018), there has been orders to close down phone lines that drug gangs use to communicate and deliver drugs through. This was implemented as a disruption tactic which would make county lines increasingly difficult to operate and therefore lower the risk of violence and exploitation experienced. There has also been an increase in raising awareness events to highlight the significance of child criminal exploitation within county lines gangs, and what practitioners can do to better support victims (Home Office, 2018).

Furthermore, Havard (2022, p.20) identified that the government began using the term "public health approach" as a part of the serious violence strategy because the harms caused by county lines drug gangs is severe and therefore deemed to be a health crisis that needs addressing by tackling the root causes. The implementation of Violence Reduction Units (VRUs) is a national response that oversees different schemes to reduce this harm. The Home Office (2023b) outlines that the focus of VRUs is to prevent serious violence through multi-agency working, the access and sharing of data across those agencies, and to target those in need with appropriate interventions throughout specific communities. These interventions were implemented in eighteen areas around England and Wales that were significantly affected by violence (Hopkins and Floyd, 2022). The government's Beating Crime Plan identifies responses from the VRUs that claim to support young people in moving away from committing violent crimes (Home Office, 2021). One response is the hospital-based navigator program that involves a specialist worker "intervening at teachable moments in A&E and custody suites shortly after involvement in violent incidents" (Home Office, 2021, p.21). The Greater Manchester VRU implemented a pilot programme within four hospitals to support young people who present with injuries because of violence. After being triaged in the emergency department the young person would be referred and assessed by a navigator to determine what support is needed if the young person

decides to engage with them; this can range from advocacy and initial support to referrals into other agencies.

An evaluation of this programme was conducted by Ellison et al (2024) who identified that referrals were made in instances where there were injuries such as knife wounds, evidence of violence, self-harm or dangerous behaviours, as well as circumstances including exploitation, domestic incidents, or criminality. Evidence provided in chapter one shows the significant level of violence within county lines gangs and therefore identifies a need to offer this specific support in hospitals for young people who are victims of CCE. Moreover, data was gathered from baseline and exit assessments done by navigators on a quarter of young people involved in this programme which revealed positive responses from young people's lifestyles, feelings of safety, mental wellbeing, and support received. The responses scored ranged from 1 (often) to 4 (never), for example, Ellison et al (2024, p.43) found that when asked "in the last month, how often have you been personally involved in or experienced violence yourself", the baseline was 2.8 compared to 3.2 on exit which shows a reduction in the young people's experience of violence. Additionally, interviews with stakeholders indicated that navigators can build better relationships with young people, especially those who have injuries that might be linked to criminality or gangs because they can be reluctant to engage with uniformed professionals (Ellison et al, 2024). This can be out of fear of repercussions or previous adverse childhood experiences with family members and agencies such as the police that means they struggle to seek help from them (Windle et al, 2020). Therefore, providing this alternative support to young people is essential in helping them to escape exploitation and reduce the harms linked with county lines.

However, there are limitations to the hospital-based navigator program that impact on its performance. Sutherland et al (2023) conducted a feasibility study on the Thames Valley VRU navigator program and found that during out-of-hours service a patient is less likely to be referred to navigators which was indicated to be because it leaves NHS workers with more work to do and there is not enough staff members to fulfil this role when the navigator workers are not on-site. This is further supported by Ellison et al (2024) who stated that when Navigators are not present within the hospital it can lead to disruption during the referral process; although NHS staff members try to ensure contact is made with the navigator over the following days, due to the significant pressure they are experiencing this is not always the case. This raises issues around the continuity of support, if a young person is a victim of CCE and is at risk of harm from gangs but is unable to access immediate support it could heighten their chances of further incidents. There are also concerns around implementing this program after the VRU funding stops and whether it will be able to maintain consistency in supporting vulnerable young people

(Ellison et al, 2024). Furthermore, this government response is only effective after a young person has been significantly harmed which is important to note because it shows that more focus needs to be placed on preventing exploitation and situations such as county lines gangs that lead to young people facing an increased risk of harm. Additionally, this links in with the ACEs Tree concept by Ellis and Dietz which suggested that young people who are surrounded by social inequality, discrimination and violence are more likely to engage in these behaviours (Windle et al, 2020), hence the need to tackle county lines gangs from within the community setting.

Moreover, the government introduced another response in 2019 known as the County Lines Programme to reduce the amount of county lines gangs and support young people and children to escape CCE (Home Office, 2024). In order to meet there aims this programme involved more funding being invested into law enforcement agencies which included four police forces in areas found to be large exporters of county lines, as well as the British Transport Police (BTP). Furthermore, this programme encompasses the National County Lines Co-ordination Centre which is vital in observing the threat of county lines gangs and organising the necessary responses to reduce it. These agencies set out to work together by locating county lines bases and then strategically closing them down through arresting the dealers and safeguarding victims. According to the Home Office (2024), between July 2024 and September 2024, 410 county lines have been closed with 557 people arrested and 851 individuals having been safeguarded by the police and subsequently referred to other services for support. These statistics demonstrate that this response is making progress in tackling these gangs and helping to support young people who have been exploited by them.

The British Transport Police plays a vital part in the county lines programme. The Home Office (2021) outlines their role which is to stop gangs spreading to different parts of the country by obstructing the flow of drugs, weapons, and cash through trainlines; as well as safeguarding the vulnerable individuals who have been exploited. Research suggests the involvement of the BTP has had positive outcomes with regards to safeguarding young people, this is evidenced by Blackburn and Smith (2021) who found that providing railway staff with awareness training on topics of county lines and exploitation helped them to identify vulnerable young people in train stations and offer them support. In one case, two young girls were found to have been exploited, were in the process of transporting crack cocaine, and were subjected to significant violence whilst on their way to a cuckooed house which was quite a distance from their own homes (Blackburn and Smith, 2021). However, although this training is useful in identifying young people who are victims of CCE and providing them with support, the scope of this government response is limited because it is unable to prevent young people from being exploited in

the first instance. As a result, it is not effective in tackling the root causes of county lines exploitation such as wider social issues that range from poverty to discrimination within communities (Windle et al, 2020) which will continue to be a significant tactic used by these gangs to coerce young people into engaging in criminal activities.

Additionally, Olver and Cockbain (2021) conducted interviews with professionals in the criminal justice sector; they found that a significant barrier in tackling county lines exploitation is a lack of intelligence and information sharing between agencies. For example, issues have been prevalent within the BTP regarding their ability to share information with other agencies such as organized crime units when noticing suspicious behaviour or vulnerable young people seen on train lines. This miscommunication leads to opportunities for enquiries being missed and victims of CCE not receiving any support. Therefore, this suggests that several agencies are not receiving adequate training in communication between forces which allows for vulnerable young people to be subjected to more harm, and needs improving. Although, it is important to note that this study only investigated professionals in the West Midlands and therefore may not be representative of the whole UK criminal justice sector but does demonstrate a lack of knowledge in some areas.

Finally, this chapter will explore the use of Trusted Adult Workers (TAWs) through the Vulnerability and Violent Crime Programme. The College of Policing was provided with a grant from the Home Office to gather evidence on serious violence issues. The aim of this strategy was to help young people who had experienced trauma because of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs), by allocating the young person a worker who would assess their level of need and then make referrals to other services, as well as work together with parents and education settings to provide the necessary support (College of Policing, 2021). This hoped to reduce the risk of them becoming involved with future criminal activity and to support them in living a healthy life with limited interference from wider social issues. This is an important aspect to tackle because as discussed in the literature review, the effect of societal disparities such as inequality, poverty, and discrimination on young people and their engagement in county lines gangs is significant; Lilly et al (2018) identifies that within Matza's (1964) theory if an individual is in a desperate situation then they are more likely to drift into criminal activities such as drug running for money or food. It is therefore necessary for researchers and the government to consider these issues when developing responses to support young people.

Moreover, an evaluation of the trusted adult workers in Portsmouth was completed by Chandan et al (2022) who found that following the completion of the Rosenberg self-esteem scale before and after support from a TAW, young people reported having higher self-esteem after working with their trusted

adult; although it is important to note that the sample size of this evaluation is small and the use of TAWs has been limited which suggests that more research is needed into the wider effectiveness of this strategy. However, there were significantly positive outcomes from this evaluation including children's educational attendance improving, a reduction in missing episodes and interactions with the police, increased resilience, and in one case a child was no longer deemed to be at risk of exploitation due to the support received from a TAW (Chandan et al, 2022). These findings indicate that working with children and young people who are at risk of serious harm from violence at an early stage, especially if the young person has already experienced ACEs, is vital in preventing the likelihood of harm in the future. Although, it is necessary to state that this government response was not targeted specifically at county lines drug gangs and CCE but is relevant and is urgently needed to support exploited young people due to the increasing threat of harm as evidenced in chapter 1. Also, as Windle et al (2020) suggested that having several ACEs will significantly increase a young person's likelihood of engaging in county lines gangs, it further supports the need to tackle these issues before the harm becomes severe. Therefore, more research and funding to develop this response may be a useful step forward in preventing this form of exploitation and in supporting young people to move away from county lines gangs.

In conclusion, this chapter has discussed the effectiveness of several different government responses in tackling CCE within county lines drug gangs. This research has shown that the objectives in these responses are similar but take different approaches. For example, the hospital-navigator programme supports young people who have been seriously injured as a result of violence, whereas the British Transport Police works to identify and safeguard vulnerable young people in train stations which county lines gangs use to distribute drugs. These interventions were effective with regards to improving young people's lives and wellbeing when receiving support from specialist workers (Ellison et al, 2024), and training staff members in railway stations has had a strong impact on identifying young people who are in need of immediate help from harmful situations (Blakeburn and Smith, 2021). However, a significant finding was that these responses focused on supporting young people after they had been exploited and significantly harmed during their involvement. Therefore, when examining the wider threat of these gangs, the findings suggest that responses should consider prevention to be one of the main priorities when tackling county lines exploitation, not just supporting young people after they have already suffered harmful experiences. Although, the Trusted Adult Worker intervention that provides support to young people who have already experienced adverse childhood experiences was found to be effective in making young people feel safer and supported; this may be useful to implement in current strategies to prevent CCE as it works with young people who are at a high risk of exploitation

(Chandan et al, 2022). Although, a further limitation with these responses was issues with funding and a lack of necessary staff members which shows that they are not functioning effectively and need improving, and some young people may be left in dangerous situations without access to support.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

The purpose of this dissertation was to explore the harms associated with County Lines drugs gangs and Child Criminal Exploitation; as well as evaluating the effectiveness of Government responses in tackling these issues. The aims included researching how and why young people are targeted by these gangs as it was important to demonstrate their role within County Lines and why they become victims of exploitation. Additionally, discussing the range of harms that young people witness and personally experience was the second aim of this project because it presents justification for this research by showing the level of danger that young people are in. Moreover, the final aim was to evaluate responses taken by the government in tackling child criminal exploitation within county lines; this is because identifying gaps in strategies and understanding areas that can be improved is essential in reducing this national threat. Furthermore, there is a lack of academic research around this topic due to County Lines gangs being relatively new within society and they are consistently evolving their techniques which supports the need for this dissertation. In this project, investigating these aims involved completing literature reviews on previous academic research using several databases. The findings were collated from a range of journal articles and research papers which helped to highlight significant information and implications for young people, as well as the Government.

To conclude this dissertation, the following section will summarise the main findings. The literature review identified the significant threat of County Lines gangs due to the large amount of drugs they are distributing and selling around the UK, as well as their decision to exploit vulnerable adults and children into engaging in criminal acts through coercion and grooming tactics. This is supported by data from the Home Office (2024) that found in 2022/23 there was estimated to be 14,000 children at risk or already exploited by county lines gangs. Furthermore, in chapter one, research identified that young people are targeted because of their perceived vulnerability, and how easily gang members could manipulate them. This is often done through offering young people material success such as money, clothes, or in some cases basic necessities such as food. This links in with Matza's (1964) theory by considering that because young people are dealing with significant levels of deprivation and have unmet needs then they are more likely to drift towards engaging in criminal behaviour as a way of surviving within today's society. This suggests that Ellis and Dietz theory of adverse childhood experiences and the impact of the community (Windle et al, 2020) does provide vital contributions to this field of research. This is because it is clear that the wider social environment such as social inequality has a significant impact on how young people end up involved within County Lines gangs.

The results of investigating the harms of CCE on young people found detrimental implications both short and long-term on their physical health such as stab wounds and on their mental wellbeing such as increased depression and paranoia. These experiences led to government responses which were found to be effective in helping young people improve their overall circumstances and implementing support to strengthen their emotional and mental wellbeing. However, a main finding was a lack of funding and staff members to provide continuous support which hindered the progress of these responses. Also, these responses were only effective after CCE, and the victimisation of children had taken place. This identified a limitation throughout these responses which is that the government is not acknowledging the need to make prevention a priority and is therefore not effectively tackling the larger issue of exploitation within County Lines drug gangs.

Moreover, choosing to do a literature-based dissertation was an appropriate decision for this research due to ethical considerations and prioritising participants wellbeing. Strengths of this project include providing answers to the research aims and gaining a stronger understanding of child criminal exploitation within county lines drug gangs. This dissertation is successful in raising awareness around young people's and their families' lived experiences of county lines gangs which is important to make known and encourage change within the government's responses to reduce further harm. However, being limited to literature-based research, this dissertation lacks primary data meaning it is relying on previous research which could have aspects that are not reliable or fully representative of the target population and therefore impact the results. Additionally, a major limitation is the need to rely on government reports and documentation in chapter two due to the limited number of academic resources on the effectiveness of these responses. This could cause issues because these reports may be subject to biases which could influence the results by creating false assumptions about the true effectiveness of these responses which could lead to unreliable data.

Subsequently, the main findings from this dissertation have identified several issues that require further development. An implication for policy is the need for national government prevention strategies that include better awareness campaigns and outreach for police, parents, education settings, and young people to outline the dangers of exploitation from these gangs. This is because it is essential to work towards preventing child criminal exploitation within county lines gangs not just supporting young people after the harm is already done. Within practice, it is evident that stronger and more consistent training is necessary to provide staff members in police, schools, social work, and even trainline workers with a detailed understanding of the signs of exploitation in young people so they are equipped to deal with situations that could save a child's life. Furthermore, additional research is vital to continue

tackling these gangs and reducing exploitation. A greater focus for researchers should be placed in understanding how social inequalities such as poverty, discrimination, and exposure to violence leads young people to take desperate acts which impacts their opportunities for their future. Therefore, what can be implemented to reduce the effects of wider social disparities on young people and them drifting into County Lines drugs gangs?

References

Andell P., and Pitts, J. (2018). The end of the line: The impact of county lines drug distribution on youth crime in a target destination. *Youth and Policy*, [Online]. Available at: The End of the Line? The Impact of County Lines Drug Distribution on Youth Crime in a Target Destination – Youth & Policy [Accessed 10 Jan. 2025].

Andell, P. and Pitts, J. (2023). *The Palgrave handbook of youth gangs in the UK*. Cham, Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan.

Ashton, S-A., and Bussu, A. (2020). Peer groups, street gangs and organised crime in the narratives of adolescent male offenders. *Journal of criminal psychology*, [Online], 10 (4), pp. 277-292. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCP-06-2020-0020> [Accessed 3 Feb. 2025].

Atkinson-Sheppard, S. (2024). Hyper-agency and county lines. *Theoretical Criminology*, [Online], 0 (0), pp. 1-16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/13624806241265677> [Accessed 21 Jan. 2025].

Atkinson-Sheppard, S., Dando, C., Ormerod, T., and Robinson, B. (2023). Coercion and crime: Convergences, divergences and ‘county lines.’ *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, [Online], 0 (0), pp. 1-23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/17488958231153981> [Accessed 19 Jan. 2025].

Blakeburn, M., and Smith, R. (2021). Exploring the role of the British Transport Police in responding to ‘County Lines’ drug markets: Enforcement and safeguarding perspectives. *The Police Journal*, [Online], 94 (2), pp. 239-256. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0032258X20902810> [Accessed 11 Mar. 2025].

Blomberg, T. G., Cullen, F. T., Carlsson, C. and Jonson, C. L. (2017). *Delinquency and drift revisited: the criminology of David Matza and beyond*. London: Routledge.

British Society of Criminology. (2015). *Statement of Ethics for Researchers in the Field of Criminology*. [Online]. Available at: Ethics – British Society of Criminology [Accessed 23 Mar. 2025].

Chandan, J., Evans, E., Abramovaite, J., Taylor, J., and Banerjee, A. (2022). Evaluation of trusted adult workers in Portsmouth: Report of additional analysis: Vulnerability and Violent Crime Programme. *College of Policing*, [Online]. Available at: Evaluation of trusted adult workers in Portsmouth: Report of additional analysis: Vulnerability and Violent Crime Programme - University of Birmingham [Accessed 3 Mar. 2025].

Clark, T., Foster, L., Sloan, L., Bryman, A. (2021). *Bryman's Social Research Methods*. Sixth Edition. Oxford University Press.

College of Policing (2021). Evaluation of the trusted adult workers role and Rock Pool train the trainer educational approach. *Vulnerability and Violent Crime interventions*. [Online]. Available at: Vulnerability and violent crime interventions | College of Policing [Accessed 24 Feb. 2025].

Coomber, R. and Moyle, L. (2018). The Changing Shape of Street-Level Heroin and Crack Supply in England: Commuting, Holidaying and Cuckooing Drug Dealers across 'County Lines'. *The British Journal of Criminology*, [Online], 58 (6), pp.1323–1342. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azx068> [Accessed 10 Nov. 2024].

Dando, C. J., Ormerod, T. C., and Atkinson-Sheppard, S. (2023). Parental experiences of the impact of grooming and criminal exploitation of children for county lines drug trafficking. *Journal of Public Health*, [Online], 45 (2), pp.346-354. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdac112> [Accessed 3 Feb. 2025].

Davies, P., and Francis, P. (2018). *Doing Criminological Research*. Third Edition. Sage Publications, Los Angeles.

Ellison, M., Krzemieniewska-Nandwani, K., Bannister, J., and Hall, B. (2024). Greater Manchester Violence Reduction Unit: Hospital Navigator Pilot - Implementation Evaluation. Project Report. *Manchester Metropolitan University, Manchester*, [Online]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.23634/MMU.00635299> [Accessed 23 Feb. 2025].

Greetham, B. (2019). *How to write your undergraduate dissertation*. Third Edition. Red Globe Press.

Harding, S. (2020). *County Lines: Exploitation and Drug Dealing Among Urban Street Gangs*. Bristol: Bristol University Press.

Harding, S. (2020). *County Lines: Exploitation and Drug Dealing Among Urban Street Gangs*. Bristol: Bristol University Press.

Havard, T. (2022). Serious youth violence: County lines drug dealing and the Government response. *House of Commons Library*, [Online]. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-9264/CBP-9264.pdf> [Accessed 18 Feb. 2025].

Havard, T. E., Densley, J. A., Whittaker, A., & Wills, J. (2023). Street gangs and coercive control: The gendered exploitation of young women and girls in county lines. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, [Online], 23 (3), pp.313-329. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/17488958211051513> [Accessed 3rd Jan. 2025].

Home Office (2018). *Serious Violence Strategy*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/serious-violence-strategy> [Accessed 18 Nov. 2024].

Home Office (2021). *Beating Crime Plan*. [Online]. Available at: Beating crime plan - GOV.UK [Accessed 23 Feb. 2025].

Home Office (2023a). *Criminal exploitation of children and vulnerable adults: county lines*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/criminal-exploitation-of-children-and-vulnerable-adults-county-lines/criminal-exploitation-of-children-and-vulnerable-adults-county-lines> [Accessed 9 Nov. 2024].

Home Office (2023b). *Violence Reduction Units 2022 to 2023*. [Online]. Available at: Violence Reduction Units 2022 to 2023 - GOV.UK [Accessed 19 Feb. 2025].

Home Office (2024). *County Lines Programme data*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.gov.uk/government/publications/home-offices-county-lines-programme-data> [Accessed 18 Nov. 2024].

Irwin-Rogers, K. (2019). Illicit Drug Markets, Consumer Capitalism and the Rise of Social Media: A Toxic Trap for Young People. *Critical Criminology*, [Online], 27, pp.591– 610. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10612-019-09476-2> [Accessed 23 Jan. 2025].

Lilly, J. R., Cullen, F. T. and Ball, R. A. (2018) *Criminological theory: context and consequences*. Seventh edition. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, Inc.

Marshall, H. (2024). Child Criminal Exploitation and the Interactional Emergence of Victim Status. *The British Journal of Criminology*, [Online], 64 (5), pp. 1011-1027. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azae008> [Accessed 12 Feb. 2025].

Maxwell, N. (2023). I'm Trying to Save My Family: Parent Experiences of Child Criminal Exploitation. *Youth Justice*, [Online], 23 (2), pp.243-258. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/14732254221122559> [Accessed 30 Jan. 2025].

Maxwell, N. (2024). 'Shove that. There's always hope': young people's lived experience of child criminal exploitation. *Journal of Youth Studies*, [Online], pp.1–17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2024.2397025> [Accessed 11 Nov. 2024].

McEwen, C. A. and Gregerson, S. F. (2019). A Critical Assessment of the Adverse Childhood Experiences Study at 20 Years. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, [Online], 56 (6), pp.790–794. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2018.10.016> [Accessed 27 Nov. 2024].

McLean, R., Robinson, G. and Densley, J.A. (2020). *County Lines: Criminal Networks and Evolving Drug Markets in Britain*. S.L.: Springer Nature.

Ministry of Justice (2024). *Knife and Offensive Weapon Sentencing Statistics: January to March 2024*. [Online]. Available at: Knife and Offensive Weapon Sentencing Statistics: January to March 2024 - GOV.UK [Accessed 31 Jan. 2025].

Moyle, L. (2019). Situating Vulnerability and Exploitation in Street-Level Drug Markets: Cuckooing, Commuting, and the ‘County Lines’ Drug Supply Model. *Journal of Drug Issues*, [Online], 49 (4), pp.739–755. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022042619861938> [Accessed 2 Nov. 2024].

National Crime Agency (2018). *County Lines Drug Supply, Vulnerability and Harm 2018*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.nationalcrimeagency.gov.uk/who-we-are/publications/257-county-lines-drug-supply-vulnerability-and-harm-2018/file> [Accessed 9 Nov. 2024].

Neaverson, A., and Lake, A. (2023). Barriers experienced with multi-agency responses to county line gangs: a focus group study. *Journal of Children’s Services*, [Online], 18 (1), pp. 61-77. Available at: <https://10.1108/JCS-03-2022-0012> [Accessed 16 Jan. 2025].

O’Hagan, A., and Edmundson, C. J. (2021). County Lines: The Exploitation of Vulnerable Members of Society. *Forensic Research & Criminology International Journal*, [Online], 9 (2), pp.47–57. Available at: <https://irep.ntu.ac.uk/id/eprint/44335> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].

O’Hagan, A., and Long, A. (2019). The socioeconomic effects of organised crimes county lines on the United Kingdom community. *Forensic Research & Criminology International Journal*,

[Online], 7 (5). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15406/frcij.2019.07.00293> [Accessed 19 Nov. 2024].

Olver, K., and Cockbain, E. (2021). Professionals' Views on Responding to County Lines-Related Criminal Exploitation in the West Midlands, UK. *Child Abuse Review*, [Online], 30 (4), pp. 347-362. Available at: Professionals' Views on Responding to County Lines-Related Criminal Exploit...: EBSCOhost [Accessed 11 Mar. 2025].

Oswald, R., Walker, S., Soppitt, S., & Irving, A. (2024). Improving the Hope of Young People impacted by Serious Violence and Child Criminal Exploitation. *The Children's Society*, [Online], pp.107. Available at: https://figshare.northumbria.ac.uk/articles/report/Improving_the_Hope_of_Young_People_impacted_by_Serious_Violence_and_Child_Criminal_Exploitation_Full_Report_May_2024/25818589/1 [Accessed 21 Feb. 2025].

Pearson, J., and Cavener, J. (2024). Professionals' understanding of the County Lines phenomenon: Insights from a study exploring the perceptions of young peoples' supported accommodation staff. *Children and Youth Services Review*, [Online], 156. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2023.107331> [Accessed 10 Jan. 2025].

Robinson, G., McLean, R. and Densley, J. (2019). Working County Lines: Child Criminal Exploitation and Illicit Drug Dealing in Glasgow and Merseyside. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, [Online], 63 (5), pp.694–711. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0306624X18806742> [Accessed 9 Nov. 2024].

Spicer, J. (2018). 'That's their brand, their business': How Police Officers are Interpreting County Lines. *Policing and Society*, [Online], 29 (8), pp.873–886. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10439463.2018.1445742> [Accessed 10 Nov. 2024].

Spicer, J., Moyle, L. and Coomber, R. (2019). The variable and evolving nature of ‘cuckooing’ as a form of criminal exploitation in street level drug markets. *Trends in Organized Crime*, [Online], 23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12117-019-09368-5> [Accessed 13th Nov. 2024].

Stone, N. (2018). Child Criminal Exploitation: ‘County Lines’, Trafficking and Cuckooing. *Youth Justice*, [Online], 18 (3), pp.285–293. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1473225418810833> [Accessed 9 Nov. 2024].

Storrod, M. L. and Densley, J. A. (2017). ‘Going viral’ and ‘Going country’: the expressive and instrumental activities of street gangs on social media. *Journal of Youth Studies*, [Online], 20 (6), pp. 677–696. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2016.1260694> [Accessed 16 Jan. 2025].

Sutherland, A., Makinson, L., Bisserbe, C., and Farrington, J. (2023). Hospital Navigators: Multi-site evaluation of practices. Evaluation Report. *Youth Endowment Fund*, [Online]. Available at: [Hospital-Navigators.-YEF-Feasibility-Study.-Jan-23.pdf](#) [Accessed 23 Feb. 2025].

Thompson, N. (2019). ‘It’s a No-Win Scenario, either the Police or the Gang Will Get You’: Young People and Organised Crime – Vulnerable or Criminal? *Youth Justice*, [Online], 19 (2), pp. 102-119. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1473225419843353> [Accessed 13 Feb. 2025].

Whittaker, A. J., Cheston, L., Tyrell, T., Higgins, M. M., Felix-Baptiste, C., and Harvard, T. (2018). From Postcodes to Profits: How gangs have changed in Waltham Forest. *London South Bank University*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.18744/PUB.002234> [Accessed 4 Feb. 2025].

Windle, J., and Briggs, D. (2015). ‘It’s like working away for two weeks’: The harms associated with young drug dealers commuting from a saturated London drug market. *Crime Prevention and Community Safety*, [Online], 17 (1), pp.105–119. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/cpcs.2015.2> [Accessed 1 Feb. 2025].

Windle, J., Moyle, L. and Coomber, R. (2020). 'Vulnerable' Kids Going country: Children and Young People's involvement in County Lines Drug Dealing. *Youth Justice*, [Online], 20 (1-2), pp.64–78. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1473225420902840> [Accessed 20 Nov. 2024].

Wood, J., and Dennard, S. (2017). 'Gang Membership: Links to Violence Exposure, Paranoia, PTSD, Anxiety, and Forced Control of Behavior in Prison'. *Psychiatry*, [Online], 80 (1), pp. 30–41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00332747.2016.1199185> [Accessed 7 Feb. 2025].

Young, S. (2022). *How to write your undergraduate dissertation in criminology*. London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.